

Case study of harmful benthic events caused by *Ostreopsis*

Elisa Berdalet^{1*}, Mireille Chinain², Marie-Yasmine Dechraoui Bottein³, Esther Garrido Gamarro⁴, Rodolphe Lemée⁵, Patricia A. Tester⁶

¹*Institut de Ciències del Mar, ICM-CSIC, Barcelona, Catalonia, Spain;* ²*Institut Louis Malardé - UMR EIO, Papeete-Tahiti, French Polynesia;* ³*Université Côte d'Azur, CNRS, UMR 7035 ECOSEAS, Nice, France; former Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations;* ⁴*Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations, Rome, Italy;* ⁵*Sorbonne Université, CNRS, Laboratoire d'Océanographie de Villefranche (UMR 7093), Villefranche-sur-Mer, France;* ⁶*Ocean Tester, LLC, Beaufort, North Carolina, U.S.A.*

*[corresponding author's email: berdalet@icm.csic.es](mailto:berdalet@icm.csic.es)

Abstract

Blooms of the benthic genus *Ostreopsis* are increasing from tropical to temperate latitudes, becoming recurrent in some beaches (especially in the Mediterranean coasts) and appearing in new zones. The main threats posed by *Ostreopsis* blooms on human health include respiratory and other problems associated with the aerosolization of toxic compounds produced by *Ostreopsis*, and potential (not clarified yet) food borne poisoning. To prevent the impacts on human health, scientists, stakeholders, and public authorities have been coordinating efforts in different Mediterranean countries via the International Agreement RAMOGE to monitor *Ostreopsis* blooms in summer periods. The gained knowledge and successful experience constitute an Early Warning System that can be translated to other BHAB cases.

Keywords: benthic harmful algal bloom, dinoflagellate, early warning system, *Ostreopsis*, palytoxin analogues

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7033169>

Introduction

The biogeographic distribution of the *Ostreopsis* species as well as their blooms have expanded from 28°S - 28°N to 45°S to 45°N since 1995. It is not known whether the species were present in the past in temperate latitudes or whether their blooms have increased in these areas due to natural and anthropogenic factors (e.g., Tester *et al.*, 2021).

The main threats posed by *Ostreopsis* blooms on human health include: i) the respiratory and other health problems associated with the aerosolization of unknown toxic compounds produced by *Ostreopsis* and ii) the risk of food borne poisoning due to the potential food web transfer (not proven yet) of palytoxins analogues (ovatoxins, ostreocins) produced by the microalga. Some *Ostreopsis* spp. blooms have also been linked to massive benthic fauna mortalities. *Ostreopsis* related respiratory cases reported in several Mediterranean beaches prompted intense scientific research and monitoring in the last two decades. Valuable information about *Ostreopsis* species taxonomy, toxin production, impacts on human health and ecosystems, driving bloom factors, biogeographic distribution, and potential impacts of climate change on their occurrence (reviewed e.g., by Pavaux *et al.*, 2020; Tester *et al.*, 2020; Zingone *et al.*, 2021) is now available. Despite *Ostreopsis* is not a priority case concerning foodborne diseases by now, given the biogeographic expansion of the genus, the blooming recurrence in some beaches, the high biomass detected in new areas (see for instance the recently documented blooms in the coast of Senegal, Brehmer *et al.* (2021)) and new massive human health outbreaks (such as

the summer event in beaches of the Bay of Biscay -Atlantic and Spanish French coasts-, with more than 700 persons impacted; pers. comm. by the French Regional Health Agency and A. Laza -EHU-) we summarize here the information about monitoring tools and strategies successfully implemented in the Mediterranean, which can be eventually used in the design of Early Warning Systems (EWSs) in other areas and other benthic harmful algal blooms (BHABs).

Case study – *Ostreopsis*

1. Description of the problem (what type of HABs)

The genus *Ostreopsis* grows in shallow and well illuminated waters, mainly attached (by a self-produced mucilage) to biotic (macroalgae, corals, bryozoans) and abiotic surfaces (rocks, sands). Cells may also detach from the substrates and become part of the plankton, forming dense aggregates of *Ostreopsis* cells at sea surface during the blooms.

The palytoxin analogues produced by some *Ostreopsis* species are high molecular weight compounds. They are determined by LC-MS/MS, although standards for the different toxins are lacking. Ovatoxins and isobaric PLTX were reported in mussels, sea urchins or fish collected in the Mediterranean coasts (reviewed by Pavaux *et al.*, 2020) at concentrations exceeding the safety alert threshold of 30 µg of PLTX-equivalent per kg of fresh flesh recommended by the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA, 2009) but, luckily, related seafood poisonings have not been reported in the Mediterranean region yet.

Nowadays, *Ostreopsis* related toxins are not regulated in Europe and thus, not monitored in marine food products. The monitoring is focused on the detection of *Ostreopsis* cells and blooms in beaches to prevent respiratory, otorhinolaryngology and cutaneous impacts on users. The toxicity effects are diverse, and not clearly associated to a particular species.

2. Information about stakeholders - Who was impacted? Were needs identified?

Ostreopsis blooms pose a main risk on beach users. In the Mediterranean, the summer vacation season coincides with the period of *Ostreopsis* blooms (in general), with potential economic cost in the touristic zones due to beach closures. Since the first health outbreaks potentially attributed to *Ostreopsis* blooms that occurred in Italy, France, Spain and Algeria, scientists were aware that an emerging HAB problem was a common threat in the Mediterranean basin. Luckily, national, and international funds for research facilitated not only scientific activities at local level, but also fostered the coordination of the research among scientists of different Mediterranean countries. Examples of such projects were MediOs in France, Ebitox in Spain and the Interreg Med coordinated project M3-HABs.

A general framework was established to structure an efficient preventive strategy, with particularities in each country (Funari *et al.*, 2015; Lemée *et al.*, 2012; Vila *et al.*, 2012; Meroni *et al.*, 2018). Fluid communication was established between scientists and the Environmental Agencies, to establish the *Ostreopsis* Monitoring program. Information about the health symptoms was also provided and determined by Public Health Authorities, and special attention was given to train related professionals in Primary Health Care

centers and hospitals, and first aid support (Red Cross and lifeguards in the beaches). Local authorities of the affected beaches were informed about the evolution of *Ostreopsis* blooms in the beach and alert signs were installed when necessary (Fig. 1) to inform the general public about the presence of the microalga, the potential symptoms, what to do and when necessary, the beach was closed. Informative brochures were elaborated by scientists with the essential information as well. Communication between scientists and the public was established through common citizen science mechanisms.

Fig. 1. Warning signs in multiple languages about the presence of *Ostreopsis* bloom with information about health symptoms for beachgoers on two Mediterranean beaches.

The international RAMOGE Agreement (www.ramoge.org) between France, Monaco and Italy, with Spain as invited participant, is facilitating the coordination among scientists of these countries, including medical professionals. Every year, prior to the summer season, virtual meetings are organized to inform about the monitoring strategies that are going to be followed in each country. After the summer period, a new meeting is held to exchange information about the balance of the season in terms of *Ostreopsis* bloom events and impacts on human health and the environment. A common database

is being elaborated with the data provided by the different institutions. The collected information during more than 10 years can allow evaluating key questions concerning risk assessment, including the sampling method as well as the alert threshold values for health symptoms, which still differ among countries. The coordination structure developed under the RAMOGE umbrella constitutes the foundation of a solid approach for the *Ostreopsis* EWS in the Mediterranean.

3. What was the development status of the country or region in terms of monitoring?

Regular monitoring of *Ostreopsis* blooms is conducted in some areas where nearly annual blooms are known to occur. Until now, most monitoring programs conduct traditional plankton samplings assuming that cells present in the water column are preferentially related to the cutaneous and respiratory impacts reported. However, the *Ostreopsis* benthic populations constitute the pool or reservoir of cells that determine the duration and maintenance of the blooms. Planktonic cells and floating aggregates transported by currents facilitate the dispersion of the bloom and the colonization of new sites. For this reason, sampling of macroalgae to estimate the *Ostreopsis* benthic population has been introduced progressively in Italy, Monaco, France, and Spain (Catalonia) as well.

4. What approach and what technology were used to solve the problem?

The most common sampling method for benthic populations is the collection of the dominant macroalgae in the area that appear covered by the mucilaginous biofilm containing *Ostreopsis* cells as described by Moreira and Tester (2016). Cell abundance is referred to as cells per gram of macroalgae

fresh weight. Plankton samples in the same area are also collected. Scientists working in the Mediterranean were soon aware that a major challenge was to find a consistent collection method to standardize cell abundances from benthic substrates. The BEDI protocol is a proposed integrative approach to estimate the cell concentration in the benthic populations and the surrounding water (Mangialajo *et al.*, 2017) while providing a direct measure of the risk associated with inhalation of aerosols. Also, the artificial substrate by Tester *et al.* (2014) has been examined and adapted in the Mediterranean and the Atlantic coast of France for *Ostreopsis* collection by Jauzein *et al.* (2018) and in the Pacific by Lee *et al.* (2020). The artificial substrate is deployed during 24 h, which integrates the diurnal variability of the cell concentrations of the benthic and planktonic *Ostreopsis* populations as recently studied in detail by Pavaux *et al.* (2021).

5. Describe EWS put in place (communication, interaction with stakeholders)

For the design of an EWS, the selection of the sampling method should be discussed, and the best strategy selected, taking into consideration logistic, technical, and human resources available in the area.

Recently, in the frame of the CoCliME project (www.coclimate.eu), an easy and reliable protocol was co-designed and implemented by scientists and stakeholders. Scientists elaborated and distributed a benthic sampling kit and provided simple training sessions on sampling. Results (*Ostreopsis* abundance) were shared between scientists and public agencies using coordinated online platforms. Microscopy cell counts were conducted at the research centres but can also be done by trained personnel and citizens provided with

microscopes (e.g., Surfrider Foundation; <https://surfrider.eu/en/>). This protocol has been successfully tested in Catalonia and France during the summers 2019 and 2020 and is described by Vila *et al.* (2022).

6. What were the forecast operation results?

The available data from some Mediterranean countries suggest that human health effects may occur at thresholds values of 2×10^5 cells g^{-1} wet weight of macroalgae and/or 3×10^4 cells L^{-1} of seawater (Lemée *et al.*, 2012; Funari *et al.*, 2015; Mangialajo *et al.*, 2017). Symptoms may not occur along the whole duration of the bloom but during certain periods (Vila *et al.*, 2016; Berdalet *et al.*, 2021). Environmental effects depend on the duration and extension of the bloom event. In the field, massive mortalities have been observed at 1.4×10^6 cells g^{-1} fresh weight of macroalgae in New Zealand (e.g., Shears and Ross, 2009) and from 250×10^6 to 3×10^9 cells L^{-1} of seawater in Italy (Sansoni *et al.*, 2003). Data on threshold cell abundances having toxic effects on different organisms have been mainly obtained from experimental ecotoxicity tests (e.g., Giussani *et al.*, 2015, 2016). The responses are variable, depending on experimental conditions and the tested organism. Overall, this information helps the authorities to provide information to the public, and to decide about the necessity to close the access to beaches.

7. What consequences did the EWS have on stakeholders' needs?

The EWS based on benthic sampling conducted by trained personnel (described in Vila *et al.*, 2021) was proven to be an effective EWS for authorities to quickly make recommendations on the health risks associated to *Ostreopsis* blooms in

Mediterranean beaches. The monitoring data protocol also contributes to the joint effort to build a time series dataset for elucidation of climate change effects on *Ostreopsis* blooms.

Conclusions

Ostreopsis is becoming an emerging issue in new (not yet monitored) areas. The problems posed by *Ostreopsis* blooms have, for now, a smaller relevance compared to *Gambierdiscus* and *Fukuyoa* blooms and Ciguatera Poisoning in the tropical regions of the world. For *Ostreopsis*, uncertainties include identification of the toxic compounds and harmful mechanisms involved in human and environmental health problems, and the future trends of the blooms under a general warming scenario. Meanwhile, the benthic nature of *Ostreopsis* and their blooms in temperate latitudes and different habitats offer the possibility to approach the challenges of addressing other potential benthic HABs and providing a template for establishing EWSs.

Acknowledgements. Scientific projects in the Mediterranean countries addressed to understand the *Ostreopsis* bloom dynamics, MediOs, Ebitox, OstreoRisk, CoClima, M3HABs, ShareMed, the Acord RAMOGE, and many others.

References

- Berdalet, E., Pavaux, A.S., Abós-Herràndiz, R., *et al.*, (2021). Abstract book ICHA19, La Paz, B.C.S. Mexico.
- Brehmeer, P., Ndiaye, W., Mbaye, A., *et al.*, (2021). Note Politique AWA, CSRP-IRD, Dakar, 13 p.

- EFSA Panel on Contaminants in the Food Chain (CONTAM); Scientific Opinion on marine biotoxins in shellfish – Palytoxin group. EFSA J. (2009), 1393.
- Funari, E., Manganelli, M., Testai, E. (2015). Harmful Algae 50, 45-56.
- Giussani, V., Sbrana, F., Asnaghi, V., *et al.*, (2015). Harmful Algae 44, 46-53.
- Giussani, V., Costa, E., Pecorino, D., *et al.*, (2016). Harmful Algae 57, 49-58.
- Jauzein, C., Fricke, A., Mangialajo, L., *et al.*, (2017). Mar. Pollut. Bull. 107, 300-304.
- Lee, L.K., Lim, Z.F., Gu, H., *et al.*, (2020). Sci. Rep. 10, 11251.
- Lemée, R., Mangialajo, L., Cohu, S., *et al.*, (2012). Cryptogam. Algol. 33, 137-142.
- Mangialajo, L., Fricke, A., Perez-Gutierrez, G., *et al.*, (2017). Harmful Algae 64, 1-10.
- Meroni, L., Chiantore, M., Petrillo, M., Asnaghi, V. (2018). Harmful Algae 80, 64-71.
- Moreira, A. and Tester, P. (2016). IOC Manuals and Guides 59.
- Pavaux, A.S., Berdalet, E., Lemée, R. (2020). Front. Mar. Sci. 7, 498.
- Pavaux, A.-S., Velasquez-Carvajal, D., Drouet, K., *et al.*, (2021). Harmful Algae 110, 102144.
- Sansoni, G., Borghini, B., Camici, G., *et al.*, (2003). Biol. Ambient. 17, 17-23.
- Shears, N.T. and Ross, P.M. (2009). Harmful Algae 8, 916-925.
- Tester, P.A., Kibler, S.R., Holland, W.C., *et al.* (2014). Harmful Algae 39, 8-25.
- Tester, P.A., Litaker, W., Berdalet, E. (2020). Harmful Algae 91, 101655.
- Vila, M., Abós-Herrándiz, R., Isern-Fontanet, J., *et al.*, (2016). Sci. Mar. 80, 107-115.
- Vila, M., Viure, L., Lemée, R., *et al.*, (2021). Abstract book ICHA19, La Paz, B.C.S. Mexico.
- Zingone, A., Escalera, L., Aligizaki, K., *et al.*, (2021). Harmful Algae 102, 101843.

